

RELATIVE INFLUENCE OF EDGE EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Delamination is one of the most critical type of damage in composite materials. It often initiates at the free edge. This phenomenon is considered to result from the strong anisotropy of mechanical properties of each individual ply, the abrupt change of material properties through the laminate thickness direction, the coupling between in plane and transverse strains and stresses near the edge of a composite laminate. Our numerical study points out singularities in $r^{-\alpha}$ for different stacking sequences. Although the singularity is very localized, we demonstrate that it is necessary to use meshes whose size of elements is equivalent to the dimension of the elementary cell to include the effect of the singularity in a delamination failure criteria.

NOTATIONS

$\epsilon_{ij}, \sigma_{ij}$	strain, stress tensor
$[a_1, \dots, a_k, \dots]$	stacking sequence
α	power of singularity
r, θ	polar coordinates

INTRODUCTION

There has been much research into the free edge effect of layered composites. The free edge effect, which arises from the fact that anyone layer in the structure is basically orthotropic, occurs when adjacent layers have different directions of orthotropy. Because of the problem involved in analytical approach and the variety of solutions put forward in the literature^{1,2,3}, it was decided to attempt a numerical approach. We used a variational approach without any hypothesis on the field displacement.

The study is confined to a simple model made up of a symmetrical stacking sequence of four layers of the same material (carbon fiber - reinforced epoxy). The material is considered as orthotropic, as stated above.

It is assumed that the specimen is long enough for the deformation at any cross section to be the same as those at the adjacent cross sections, then, only the transverse variables (y and z) need to be considered.

DESCRIPTION OF SPECIMEN

The specimen was first considered as consisting of four layers of fiber (T300) and epoxy resin (Narmco 5208). The fibers in each layer are parallel, but arranged in successive layers in the order a_1, a_2, a_2, a_1 , so that the specimen has mirror symmetry about plane $z=0$. The usual notation for this arrangement is $(a_1, a_2)_s$.

Dimensions were taken as in figure 1 : ply thickness 0.2 mm, total thickness of specimen

0.8 mm, specimen width 4 mm, specimen length very large as compared with its transverse dimensions.

It should be noticed that these dimensions were chosen to isolate the localized behaviour problem which was the subject of the study, rather than referring to any practical application.

PHYSICAL PROBLEM

A pure tensile stress is applied along the Ox axis of the specimen and the stress state in the material is examined at a cross section sufficiently far from each end. Then a finer examination is made around point A which is the intersection between the a₁, a₂ interface and the free edge.

ANALYSIS AND FINITE-ELEMENT IDEALIZATIONS

Given the mentioned hypothesis, the problem can be studied in a quasi-three-dimensional approximation (following in this Pipes and Pagano⁴). The used finite-elements are of course very near from those developed in references⁵ and ⁶.

Assuming the specimen to be very long, which means that local distortions induced by the applied load are spread out to infinity, we can state that the strains in a given cross section are identical to those in neighbouring cross sections, or in other words, strains are independent of the space variable x.

In terms of displacement, we could say that there will be first a relative displacement of the cross section along Ox axis and then all the cross sections will warp in the same way.

Consequently it writes:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x,y,z) &= \epsilon_{xx}^G + U(y,z) \\ v(x,y,z) &= V(y,z) \\ w(x,y,z) &= W(y,z) \end{aligned}$$

These expressions induce the following strain components:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= \epsilon_{xx}^G + \epsilon_{xx}(y,z) & \epsilon_{yz} &= \epsilon_{yz}(y,z) \\ \epsilon_{yy} &= \epsilon_{yy}(y,z) & \epsilon_{zx} &= \epsilon_{zx}(y,z) \\ \epsilon_{zz} &= \epsilon_{zz}(y,z) & \epsilon_{xy} &= \epsilon_{xy}(y,z) \end{aligned}$$

Four-noded isoparametric elements were used to discretize a quarter of a cross section.

Each element has 13 degrees of freedom: 3 displacements per node plus one (ϵ_{xx}^G) which is common to all the quadrilaterals in the section. The modeled specimen was a carbon epoxy T300 Narmco 5208 composite with the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{1111} &= 145000 \text{ MPa} \\ C_{2222} &= 12700 \text{ MPa} \\ C_{1122} &= 6720 \text{ MPa} \\ C_{1212} &= 9700 \text{ MPa} \\ C_{2323} &= 6480 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Each ply was supposed to be transversally isotropic. As stated in the introduction, our purpose was to investigate the stresses around point A (figure 1). The used meshes were therefore coarse near the center of the cross section and much finer around point A. Since a singularity is expected at this point, our mesh was radiating from this point in order to examine any singularity in polar coordinates (r, θ) (figure 2). The length of the elements varies from 10^{-3} m to 10^{-10} m. The circular part of the mesh is characterized by three quantities: the ratio of the geometrical progression of circles, the number of circles and the number of sectors.

Fig. 1. Specimen model geometry.

Fig. 2. Finite element mesh.

STUDY OF $[\pm 45]_s$

Plate theory gives the value of different stresses at the center. Near the point A, the problem is clearly different. The results obtained with different mesh sizes reveal that a singularity exists which is obviously of power type (figure 3). The components σ_{yy} , σ_{yz} and σ_{xy} of the stress tensor are studied along the interface and the free edge and we can observe that, in the vicinity of point A, their values increase with mesh refinement and that a plot in Log-Log axis exhibits a singularity in $r^{-\alpha}$ (figure 4). Further, if we draw σ_{xz} , σ_{zz} as a function of $r^{-\alpha}$, we get straight lines which indicates a dependency in θ with a common point on y axis (figure 5). We can write a general expression as:

$$\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) = f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha} + g_{ij} \quad \text{with} \quad g_{yy} = g_{xy} = g_{yz} = 0$$

Fig. 3. σ_{xz} at interface $(+45, -45)_s$ composite.

Fig. 4. $\text{Log } \sigma_{xy}$ and σ_{yz} function of $\text{Log } r$ $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$.

σ_{xx} is obtained using the stress-strain relations; consequently this component presents the same type of singularity. For a $(+45, -45)_s$, we find $\alpha=0.0476$. This result is in good agreement with analytical results⁷. If we admit this value of α , another series of curves gives $f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha}$ for different radii:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= .228 \cdot 10^{-8} \\ r_2 &= .146 \cdot 10^{-6} \\ r_3 &= .933 \cdot 10^{-5} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 5. $\text{Log } \sigma_{xz}$ versus $\text{Log } r$ for different polar angles θ ($+45, -45$)_s composite.

These results are plotted on figures 6 and 7. It was necessary to validate these results on other sequences.

Fig. 6. $f_{xz}(\theta)$ for different radii r [$\pm 45^\circ$]_s.

Fig. 7. $f_{xy}(\theta)$ for different radii $r [\pm 45^\circ]_s$.

STUDY OF OTHER SEQUENCES

In that case, the regular part of stress depends on θ and the global stress is given by:

$$\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) = f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha} + g_{ij}(\theta)$$

Value of α

If we consider q , the ratio of the geometric progression of the mesh and three radii r_1, r_2, r_3 with $r_2 = q r_1$, $r_3 = q r_2$ and

$$\sigma_{ij}(r_k, \theta) = f_{ij}(\theta)r_k^{-\alpha} + g_{ij}(\theta) \quad k=1,2,3$$

we find:

$$\alpha = \frac{\text{Log}[\sigma_{ij}(r_2, \theta) - \sigma_{ij}(r_1, \theta)] - \text{Log}[\sigma_{ij}(r_3, \theta) - \sigma_{ij}(r_2, \theta)]}{\text{Log } q}$$

and for the different sequences

$+a_1/-a_2$	$1-\alpha$
$+45/-45$	0.953
$50/-40$	0.951
$60/-30$	0.9367
$70/-20$	0.916
$80/-10$	0.899
$90/0$	0.892

Determination of $f_{ij}(\theta)$

For two different radii r_1, r_2 we get:

$$\sigma_{ij}(r_1, \theta) = f_{ij}(\theta)r_1^{-\alpha} + g_{ij}(\theta)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}(r_2, \theta) = f_{ij}(\theta)r_2^{-\alpha} + g_{ij}(\theta)$$

so

$$f_{ij}(\theta) = \frac{\sigma_{ij}(r_2, \theta) - \sigma_{ij}(r_1, \theta)}{r_2^{-\alpha} - r_1^{-\alpha}}$$

The difference $\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) - f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha}$ gives the value of $g_{ij}(\theta)$. First, if we compare the irregular part of stress $f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha}$ and the regular part $g_{ij}(\theta)$, these quantities are of the same order. Second, if we compare the single singular part of the stress with the summation of the regular and irregular part, we notice that the two quantities differ very rapidly. That means that the singularity is very localized. At a distance of 10^{-5} m (which is, physically speaking the size of the elementary cell) of the point A, a difference of 40% can be noticed. This distance will be used as a critical distance for our finite element meshes.

APPLICATION TO INDUSTRIAL STACKING SEQUENCES

Initiation and evolution of damage is characterized by:

- first transverse cacking in the more desoriented plies
- delamination at the edge of the specimen
- final rupture of the composite

In fact, these phenomena depend on the stacking sequences which are more or less able to delaminate. The beginning of this study shows that the singularity due to edge effect is very localized and that it is not necessary to take into account a local effect but to have a refined mesh whose size of the finer elements is acceptable compared to the physical constituents of the material.

If we choose two quasi-isotropic stacking sequences $[0, +45, -45, 90]_s$ and $[0, 90, +45, -45]_s$, it can be shown that one of them is bound to delaminate more easily than the other. The maximum stress σ_{zz} is drawn on figure 8. For $[0, +45, -45, 90]_s$, σ_{zz} is higher at the interface $[45, 90]$. This result is in good agreement with experimental results. Further for $[0, 90, +45, -45]_s$, the maximum stress σ_{zz} is negative at the interface $[+45, -45]$ and for the applied force, it is 40% lower at the interface $[45, 90]$ than the higher stress σ_{zz} at the interface $[-45, 90]$ in the sequence $[0, +45, -45, 90]_s$. Consequently this last sequence should delaminate more easily than the other one. In the same way, it is possible to analyse sequences with a great number of plies (32 plies) and to predict the ability of each sequence to delaminate. The only restriction is to have a mesh whose the finer element is equal to 10^{-5} m which is physically a fiber wrapped into matrix. So the local effect of the singularity can influence the global state of the material.

CONCLUSION

The singularity due to that we commonly call the "edge effect" can be written for different stacking sequences as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = f_{ij}(\theta)r^{-\alpha} + g_{ij}(\theta)$$

First, it appears that this singularity is very localized and do not spray a distance equal to 10^{-5} m from the edge. Second, the regular part of the stress $g_{ij}(\theta)$ can also be very important. To study different stacking sequences and the capacity of delamination at each interface, it is necessary to have a finite element formulation whose finer element is equal to that critical distance 10^{-5} m to affect the global state of the material by the local singularity. So it is necessary to consider this phenomenon while staying reasonable for the physical scale of the material.

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